

PROMOTION OF CHESS IN FAMILY-NEIGHBORHOOD PARTNERSHIP

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7262828>

Annotations The fame of chess players who grew up in communities that effectively use chess for meaningful spending of their free time is becoming known throughout the world. It is difficult to say that sports events organized with young people in all districts are in demand. If we look at this issue from a regional point of view, then in some rural and urban areas this issue is resolved more positively, and in the vicinity of the youth leisure is to a certain extent regulated through participation in various sports and sports competitions. Events. However, the issue of organizing leisure time for young people in some communities has not yet been fully resolved. This is directly related to the level of sports events organized in each area and their level. Today, community activists working in the community on a community basis: community leaders, consultants, trainers, educators, demonstrate the need to prioritize their methods of work, mainly in the field of physical education of young people.

Key words: chess, community, coaches, national values, sports, perception, thinking, memory and logical thinking.

INTRODUCTION

Harmonious upbringing of the younger generation is the age-old dream of our people. The formation of a modern personality on the basis of spiritual, moral, national, cultural, historical traditions and universal values is the main task facing parents, schools and the public. community. is one of the responsibilities.

Our national ideology and values reflect the goals of our people. Children see the social and spiritual image of society in the image of a family, and for the first time understand the essence of society's needs in this small community.

The role of the family, especially of educational institutions, is important in instilling in them basic spiritual and moral knowledge. The main task of educational institutions, family and public committees, social institutions is to help the idea of national independence become the spiritual heritage of all our youth, introduce it into their worldview, and explain its essence.

Thirty percent of the population is between 14 and 30 years old. Modern conditions and opportunities have been created for them to receive education and acquire a profession. At the same time, it is important to organize

meaningful leisure activities for young people. The more mature the youth is spiritually, the stronger will be their immunity to various vices.

As you know, the head of our state put forward 5 important initiatives to organize work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres on the basis of the new system.

It is positive that the life of people living in the territory that is part of local government, its healthy lifestyle, socio-economic development are in constant attention of our government. Therefore, using all the positive features of this social structure, it is important to increase the interest of young people in chess.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY (LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY)

We know from the past that our ancestors used chess as a necessity. The fact that among our people there are many people with the qualities of agility, intelligence, creativity and will is reflected in the writings of our great scientists. According to historical sources, the Uzbek people considered chess as a means of physical education. The people respected a chess player who personified strength, endurance, will and courage of working people, moral purity. Chess competitions were held on family holidays, in their free time. These competitions are especially popular during the Navruz holiday. It was attended by chess players from different cities and villages.

The works of our great scientists, writers and scholars Abu Ali ibn Sino (980-1037), Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) describe the competition of strong chess players and describe some methods. From these works it is clear that the Uzbeks had a fairly developed system of chess techniques.

The role of chess in the development of human thinking has been highlighted in many studies (M. Mukhiddinov, R. Evkaev, A. Tashkhodzhaev). There are also many examples in historical sources of how great historical figures (Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur, etc.) used chess in their work.

Today, in the makhallas of the Syrdarya region, certain work is being carried out to highlight the leisure of youth, based on chess. The fame of chess players who grew up in communities that effectively use chess for meaningful spending of their free time is becoming known throughout the world.

However, it is difficult to say that sports events organized with young people in all districts are in demand. If we look at this issue from a regional point of view, then in some rural and urban areas this issue is resolved more positively, and in the vicinity of the youth leisure is to a certain extent regulated through

participation in various sports and sports competitions. Events. However, the issue of organizing leisure time for young people in some communities has not yet been fully resolved. This is directly related to the level of sports events organized in each area and their level. Today, community activists working in the community on a community basis: community leaders, consultants, trainers, educators, demonstrate the need to organize their working methods with an emphasis on the physical education of young people.

DISCUSSION

The following methods should be used to attract young people to play chess in the neighborhood and thus promote the sport of chess.

1. Every parent should start with a family in order to interest children in sports, realizing that chess is a national value.
2. Community activists and sports instructors need to know the balance between the mental and physical condition of young people in relation to chess.
3. The youth of the district should get used to creating a state of high activity in chess practice with the help of their available opportunities.
4. Community activists should take all necessary measures to instill in young people such qualities as mental and physical stability, endurance, and make them healthy young men and women.

We all know that parenting begins in the family. Discipline is a process aimed at shaping the mind, behavior and all-round development of a person towards a goal. Because in the process of upbringing in the family, not only knowledge, skills and abilities are acquired, but also moral convictions, feelings, moral, volitional and physical qualities, character traits of the Uzbek people.

Given the fact that chess is a national value, we are all responsible for making it a universal human value, popularizing it in society, and there are opportunities to introduce Uzbek youth to the world, this must be accepted. a more serious question.

As the role of physical education and sports in social development increases, so does the need to guide young people from neighboring areas to chess. Based on the above, the main factors in the popularization of chess in the district are:

1. Determine the level of interest in chess in the district.
2. Community and parent collaboration
3. Promotion of the activities of strong athletes from the community.
4. Relive mentors and mentors who work with the community.

The most important thing is that parents understand and feel the importance of playing chess for the physical and spiritual development of young people.

RESULTS

Based on the above considerations, we also propose the following, given that it is possible to form a conscious attitude towards chess in young people and, thus, to popularize chess in society.

1. To form the perception of chess among the youth of the quarter based on their age characteristics;
2. To form in parents a positive impression of the game of chess, which is our national value, our national pride;
3. Fostering interest in chess in the family and in preschool;
4. To widely promote the activities of the world and Asian champions who grew up in our country, to set an example for them;
5. To acquaint young people with the activities of local sports masters;
6. Building partnerships between community and family through chess.

With the above in mind, it would be a good idea to popularize chess among young people in partnership with the community:

- 1) The positive perception of chess is expanding;
- 2) Increasing opportunities to educate young people physically strong and healthy;
- 3) their free time is organized voluntarily;
- 4) the number of young people involved in sports will increase;
- 5) The frequency of unrest among young people has decreased.

OUTPUT

In short, by playing chess at an early age, they grow and develop their perception, thinking, memory and logical thinking.

The idea is to develop the thinking of children by playing chess. As Professor V. Alimasov wrote: "Only vigilant thinking teaches people to live vigilantly." Chess is a thought-provoking game, art, sport. Learning about this universal game, practicing it, and teaching kids will teach us all to think for ourselves and stay alert through independent thinking.

Recommendations:

1. Strategy of actions of the President of Uzbekistan in five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021. January 7, 2017.
2. Five important initiatives put forward by the President of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.
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